

Synthesis of 1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydro-2-Methyl-3-Benzyl-1,4-Dioxo-Pyrazino (1. 2-a) Indole

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Johnson and his coworkers¹ obtained 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,3-dimethyl-1,4-dioxopyrazino(1,2-a)indole (V, R = CH₃) on warming the antibiotic, gliotoxin (I) with red phosphorus and hydriodic acid in acetic acid. They² also synthesised this pyrazinoindole in connection with their studies on the structure of gliotoxin following Robinson^{3,4}. Indole-2-carbonyl chloride (II) was condensed with ethyl ester of dl-N-methylalanine (III, R = CH₃)

to give indole-2-carboxyl-N-methylalanine ethyl ester (IV, R = CH₃). This ester cyclised to give the pyrazinoindole (V, R = CH₃) in the presence of the same amino acid ester.

As mentioned in our earlier publication⁵, 10-hydroxy-1,4-dioxopyrazinoindoles were also synthesised following the same method. 3-Methoxyindole-2-carbonyl chloride on condensing with excess of amino acid esters gave the corresponding 10-methoxy pyrazinoindoles. On demethylation of 10-methoxy derivatives with hydriodic acid and phosphorus¹, 10-hydroxy pyrazinoindoles were obtained.

We prepared 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-methyl-3-benzyl-1,4-dioxopyrazino(1,2-a)indole (V, R = CH₂ C₆H₅) by condensing indole-2-carbonyl chloride (II) with excess of ethyl ester of dl-N-methylphenylalanine (III, R = CH₂ C₆H₅).

EXPERIMENTAL

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-3-benzyl-1,4-dioxopyrazino(1,2-a)indole : Indole-2-carboxylic acid (1.6 g; 0.01 mole) was converted to indole-2-carbonyl chloride (II) by treating with 2.3 g;

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(1.4 ml., 0.02 mole) of thionyl chloride⁶. The anhydrous ethereal solution of indole-2-carbonyl chloride was reacted with excess of N-methylphenylalanine ethyl ester (III, R = CH₂ C₆H₅) in dry ether (prepared by esterification of 5.3 g., 0.03 mole of N-methylphenylalanine). The mixture turned cloudy immediately, and on standing for twenty four hours an oil deposited at the bottom of the reaction flask. This was presumably N-methylphenylalanine ester hydrochloride. The clear supernatant ethereal solution was decanted, washed with water

twice to free it from traces of ester hydrochloride and dried over sodium sulphate. After filtering and evaporating the solution to dryness on a steam bath, 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-methyl-3-benzyl-1,4-dioxopyrazino(1,2-a)indole (V, R = CH₂ C₆H₅) was obtained as a semi-solid mass. It was crystallised from dry benzene, m.p. 125°, yield 2.3 g., 76% (calculated on the basis of indole-2-carboxylic acid taken). (Found: C, 74.95; H, 5.4; N, 9.1. C₁₀H₁₆O₂N₂ required C, 75.0; H, 5.3; N, 9.2).

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